

THE CONTENT AND ESSENCE OF THE DESERTIFICATION PROBLEM AND ITS GEOGRAPHICAL ASPECTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19091101>

Abstract: This thesis analyzes the pedagogical principles of language learning skills development based on the Montessori methodology. The study highlights the importance of the Montessori approach in the development of students' speech activity, independent thinking and communicative competence in the process of primary education. Also, the effectiveness of the principles of free choice, individual approach, sensory development and practical activity-based teaching in the process of language learning is scientifically and theoretically substantiated. The pedagogical possibilities of the Montessori methodology in strengthening students' motivation for independent learning and systematically forming language competencies are analyzed.

Keywords: language learning skills, primary education, communicative competence, individual approach, independent learning, speech activity, didactic tools.

Introduction.

In today's era of accelerated globalization, information exchange and communication processes, a person's mastery of the language is becoming one of the most important factors determining not only the quality of education, but also his social activity, intellectual potential and future professional success. The issue of the correct, consistent and effective formation of language learning skills in students, especially at the primary education stage, is one of the priority areas of pedagogical science. Because it is during this period that the child's speech activity, hearing and perception skills, vocabulary, culture of expression of thought and communicative experience develop rapidly. Therefore, the use of modern and effective methodologies in the language teaching process that are appropriate to the age and psychophysiological characteristics of the student and take into account his natural developmental needs is of urgent importance. In traditional educational practice, language teaching is often organized based on the transfer of ready-made knowledge, memorization of rules and repeated performance of exercises. Such an approach in some cases cannot sufficiently ensure the student's active speech practice, independent thinking, understanding and use of language units and internal motivation. As a result, the student may become a passive subject in the process of learning a language, his interest in learning may wane, and he may have difficulties in applying his knowledge in practical speech situations. Therefore, today, the need for pedagogical approaches that put the student at the center of the educational process, taking into account

his natural pace of development and individual needs, is growing. One of such effective and humane pedagogical approaches is the Montessori methodology. This methodology serves to direct the child to independent activity, encourage him to learn on the basis of free choice, and naturally form knowledge, skills and competencies in him through a specially prepared developmental environment. In the Montessori educational philosophy, the child is valued as a person, his internal capabilities, interests and pace of development are respected. This is of particular importance in the process of language learning. Because language is the main means of human thinking, communication, socialization and self-expression. In the process of developing language skills, it is important for the child to learn independently, through their senses, to naturally perceive words and sounds, and to enrich their speech experience through practical exercises.

A distinctive feature of the Montessori methodology is that the educational process is organized not on the basis of coercion or strict control, but on the basis of the child's internal needs and interests. In this case, the student is given the opportunity to independently choose his activities, complete tasks within his capabilities, and understand and correct his mistakes. It is these aspects that are of particular pedagogical importance in the formation of language learning skills. Because language acquisition is manifested not only in knowing grammatical rules, but also in the unity of multifaceted speech activities such as listening, understanding, pronunciation, speaking, reading and writing. The Montessori approach allows these skills to be developed in an interconnected manner, based on natural and active learning. The language learning process for primary school students should, first of all, be interesting, practical and emotionally comfortable. Because children of this age learn faster and more effectively based on concrete objects, visual aids, movement exercises, and sensory experience than on abstract rules. In the Montessori methodology, these factors are given priority. Sensory materials, phonetic exercises, tools that help understand the relationship between sounds and letters, and tasks designed for independent work increase children's interest in learning the language. At the same time, this methodology enhances speech activity in students, expands their vocabulary, develops pronunciation accuracy, and serves the consistent formation of written and oral speech.

The relevance of the topic is that today, the requirements for teaching based on a competency-based approach are increasing in the education system. Such an approach requires the student not only to acquire knowledge, but also to apply it in practical situations, think independently, enter into dialogue, and express his or her thoughts fluently. The formation of language learning skills is also closely related to the development of communicative, cognitive, and practical competencies. The Montessori methodology, with its free activity, internal

discipline, independent self-management and research-based nature, fully meets the requirements of the competency-based approach. Therefore, the scientific and pedagogical substantiation and application of Montessori principles in the formation of language learning skills is an important scientific and practical issue.

The need to study this topic is also explained by the fact that although research on the Montessori methodology has largely covered issues of general developmental, moral, aesthetic and sensory education, there is a need for a systematic analysis of the principles of language learning skills formation as a special pedagogical problem. In particular, an in-depth study of the possibilities of this methodology in primary education practice in speech development, the gradual formation of language competencies, ensuring student independence and strengthening communicative activity is considered an urgent scientific task. After all, today's educational process is not limited to simply imparting knowledge, but also involves developing an active life position in the student, a culture of free expression of one's own thoughts, and social communication skills.

The study of the principles of language learning skills formation using the Montessori methodology is of great importance not only theoretically, but also practically. This approach serves to improve the language acquisition process in primary education in accordance with the laws of natural development of students, increase the effectiveness of education, develop students' independent work skills and form them as active communicative subjects. Also, pedagogical recommendations, methodological approaches and didactic tools developed on the basis of this methodology enrich the activities of teachers and allow the educational process to reach a new level in terms of content and quality. The issue of the principles of language learning skills formation using the Montessori methodology is of important scientific and practical importance from the point of view of modern pedagogy. It serves to take into account the individual development characteristics of children, to organize natural and conscious language acquisition, independent learning activities and to reveal effective mechanisms for the formation of communicative competence. Therefore, elucidating the theoretical foundations of this topic, revealing its pedagogical content and analyzing its practical possibilities is one of the urgent tasks of today's education.

Discussion.

The issue of forming language learning skills is one of the most urgent areas of modern pedagogy and methodological science. This issue is especially important at the stage of primary education, since it is during this period that the child's speech activity, thinking, perceptual abilities, vocabulary and communicative experience develop rapidly. From this point of view, discussing the principles of forming language learning skills using the Montessori

methodology is important not only from the methodological point of view, but also from the point of view of the concept of person-oriented education. Because in this approach, the student is not a receiver of ready-made knowledge, but a subject who independently assimilates knowledge, understands it on the basis of experience and naturally develops his speech activity.

The main idea of the Montessori methodology is to reveal the child's internal capabilities, relying on the laws of natural development. This approach is especially effective in the process of language learning. The reason is that language is a complex communicative phenomenon that is formed not under the external forced influence of a person, but in the process of social environment, hearing, observation, repetition, imitation and practical application. The Montessori methodology places special emphasis on this principle of naturalness. That is, the child learns language not only as a set of rules, but as a means of vital communication. This forms in the student a natural, not artificial, interest in language, an internal need and active motivation.

In the discussion, it should be noted, first of all, that the person-oriented nature of the Montessori methodology is an important factor in the development of language learning skills. In the traditional lesson process, the same tasks, the same pace, and the same result criteria are applied to all students. This does not allow for full consideration of individual differences, in particular, the peculiarities of language perception, memorization, pronunciation, and use in speech. In the Montessori methodology, each child is seen as a separate individual. He is given the opportunity to choose activities that correspond to his own pace of development, interests, and level of preparation. The advantage of this approach to language learning is that some children can distinguish sounds faster, while others may be more active in logically connecting words or constructing sentences. Therefore, an individual approach allows language skills to be formed not in a single rhythm, but naturally, in accordance with the student's internal development trajectory.

A specially prepared educational environment plays a special role in the Montessori approach. The role of the environment in the process of language learning is invaluable. The child first hears, sees, compares, names the language, and then, having mastered it, uses it in active speech. In the Montessori methodology, the environment is organized not just as a place where lessons are held, but as a pedagogical system that encourages the student to independent learning, stimulates speech activity, and helps to understand words and concepts on a subject-based basis. In such an environment, each didactic material has its own purpose, its own place, and its own pedagogical function. Materials intended for language learning serve to understand the sound-letter relationship, expand vocabulary, develop pronunciation accuracy, prepare for reading and writing, and

form independent speech activity. As a result, the child masters the language not as an abstract system, but in connection with concrete activities and sensory experiences. One of the important principles of the Montessori methodology is free choice. This principle is often misinterpreted and can be perceived as chaos or lack of control. In fact, freedom in the Montessori system is manifested in harmony with internal discipline, responsibility and conscious activity. Giving the student the opportunity to freely choose in the process of learning a language helps him master language units based on his internal need. For example, when a child independently chooses to work with certain word cards, practice sounds, name objects or observe letter shapes, he enters into the activity not out of obligation, but out of interest. This ensures the stability of mastery. From a pedagogical point of view, if compulsory activity often gives superficial results, then activity based on internal interest leads to deeper mastery. The principle of sensory development in the formation of language learning skills also deserves a separate discussion. According to the Montessori concept, a child's mental development is formed on the basis of experience received through the senses. Language is also mastered primarily through hearing, seeing, feeling and movement. In this sense, sensory materials, exercises for distinguishing sounds, tasks aimed at finding the harmony of the subject and the name, preparatory work for writing related to hand movements form the foundation of language learning. Especially for children of primary age, it is more effective to first understand language units based on sensory experience than to teach abstract grammatical concepts all at once. In the Montessori methodology, the processes of seeing the shape of a letter, feeling it with your hands, hearing its sound and pronouncing it are organized together. This multi-channel learning leaves a strong mark in the child's memory and facilitates language learning.

During the discussion, it is also necessary to separately note the possibilities of the Montessori methodology in organizing independent learning. The sustainable formation of language learning skills is not limited to explanations and instructions in the lesson. The student must be able to manage his own activities, independently find his mistakes, and understand the need for repetition and practice. It is in this respect that the Montessori methodology has a strong pedagogical potential. In it, the teacher does not act as a central controller, but as a guide, observer, and creator of favorable conditions. This turns the student from a passive receiver into a person inclined to active research. The formation of independence in language learning is of great importance for the student to expand his vocabulary, express his thoughts independently, work with text, and behave freely in speech situations. Another important aspect of the Montessori methodology is the unique organization of the attitude to errors in it. In traditional education, mistakes are often negatively assessed, and the student's

performance can be corrected on the basis of external control. In the Montessori system, mistakes are considered a natural part of development. Most didactic materials have a self-monitoring feature, and the child can find and correct his own mistakes. This is of great importance in language learning, because if the student is not afraid of mistakes, he will speak more actively, write more, and try more. This develops verbal courage. Verbal courage is an important component of communicative competence. Thus, the error-tolerant approach in the Montessori methodology provides psychological comfort in the language learning process and stimulates the student's free speech activity. When discussing this approach, it is also necessary to pay attention to the principle of communicativeness. The main goal of language learning is not to memorize rules, but to be able to communicate, express thoughts, understand conversations, and build meaningful speech. The Montessori method promotes language acquisition through natural communication, object naming, conversation, storytelling, questioning, and observation. This approach interprets language not as a theoretical subject separated from life, but as a tool for direct practical needs. Therefore, through the Montessori method, students develop not only linguistic knowledge, but also communicative competencies. This is fully consistent with the modern competency-based paradigm of education.

Also, the role of the teacher in the application of the Montessori methodology to the language learning process takes on a new meaning. The teacher is not the only source of knowledge, but also participates as a specialist who observes the individual capabilities of the child, provides him with appropriate pedagogical assistance and creates the necessary developmental environment. This increases the independence and activity of the student in the educational process. At the same time, the teacher has the opportunity to differentially organize the language learning process by identifying the stage of speech development, interests and difficulties of each child. Therefore, the effectiveness of the Montessori methodology largely depends on the teacher's observation, methodological preparation and ability to properly organize the educational environment. However, some difficulties may also be observed in the process of applying this methodology to language learning. In particular, the lack of the necessary material and didactic base for the full organization of the Montessori environment in all educational institutions, the lack of special training of teachers in this methodology, and in some cases the possibility of conflicts between the traditional assessment system and the Montessori approach. Also, factors such as the number of students in the classroom, the learning environment, and cooperation with parents are important for the full application of the Montessori methodology. Therefore, it is necessary to approach the issue of implementing this methodology in practice not only as a theoretical ideal, but also from the point

of view of specific pedagogical conditions and real opportunities. It is clear that the pedagogical potential of the Montessori methodology in the formation of language learning skills is extremely high. It serves to form in students independent thinking, freedom of speech, perception based on intuition, internal discipline, and reading and writing skills appropriate to the pace of individual development. Most importantly, this methodology connects the process of language learning with the natural needs and active experience of the child. As a result, language learning turns from an artificial obligation into a natural need, from external control into internal management, from repetition of a ready-made model into an independent speech activity.

Discussion of the principles of forming language learning skills using the Montessori methodology shows that this approach can be an important methodological basis for modern primary education. It allows for a more effective organization of language education, focusing on the child's personal capabilities, natural development patterns, internal motivation and communicative needs. Therefore, a deeper integration of the principles of the Montessori methodology into the practice of language learning, the development of methodological recommendations based on them, and the improvement of the teacher training system can be considered an urgent pedagogical task.

Conclusion.

Analysis of the issue of forming language learning skills using the Montessori methodology shows that this approach has effective pedagogical opportunities in ensuring the speech development of students in the process of primary education. Language is the main tool for human thinking, communication and socialization, and the process of learning it gives high results only when it is organized based on the laws of natural development. Based on this principle, the Montessori methodology allows the formation of language skills, taking into account the individual developmental characteristics, interests and internal needs of the child. Also, the Montessori methodology serves to develop independent thinking, research activity and communicative competence of students in the process of language learning. In this, the teacher participates not as the main source of knowledge, but as a pedagogue who guides, monitors and creates a developing environment for the educational process. This increases the activity of students in the educational process and encourages them to learn independently. As a result, the language learning process becomes not a mandatory activity, but an interesting and meaningful activity for the student.

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